

A STUDY ON THE CORRELATION OF VITAMIN D AND INSULIN RESISTANCE IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Background: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a metabolic disorder often associated with insulin resistance (IR). Emerging research suggests vitamin D may influence insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism. **Objective:** This study investigates the correlation between serum vitamin D levels and insulin resistance in patients with T2DM. **Material & Method:** A case-control study was conducted involving 90 Cases (45 T2DM patients) and 45 healthy controls aged 30 to 60 years. Fasting blood glucose, Serum insulin and vitamin D levels were estimated. HOMA-IR was calculated for insulin resistance. **Results:** T2DM were having higher mean fasting glucose levels ($p < 0.001$) as compared to controls. Although serum Insulin levels were within the normal range in cases and controls but significantly less in T2DM as compared to controls ($p < 0.003$). However, HOMA-IR was significantly elevated in T2DM as compared to controls ($p < .001$). Vitamin D levels were significantly decreased in T2DM as compared to controls ($p = 0.003$). **Conclusion:** The above findings suggest a significant inverse relationship between serum vitamin D levels and insulin resistance in T2DM patients. Vitamin D deficiency may contribute to insulin resistance, indicating the potential role of vitamin D supplementation in the management of T2DM.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Insulin Resistance, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, HOMA-IR, Serum Insulin.

INTRODUCTION

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disease characterized by persistent hyperglycemia and insulin resistance due to beta-cell dysfunction. It represents a major global public health burden, with an increasing prevalence influenced by lifestyle and genetic factors. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimates that in 2021, approximately 536.6 million adults worldwide were living with diabetes, and this number is projected to rise to 783.2 million by 2045 [1].

In the Indian context, the dual burden of T2DM and widespread vitamin D deficiency presents a unique healthcare challenge. Studies conducted in various regions of India have consistently demonstrated that a significant proportion of the population suffers from hypovitaminosis D, with levels below the recommended threshold of 30 ng/mL [2]. Vitamin D, classically associated with calcium and bone metabolism, is now recognized for its broader roles, including immune regulation and modulation of glucose metabolism. The presence of vitamin D receptors (VDR) in various insulin-sensitive tissues, such as pancreatic beta cells, skeletal muscles, and adipose tissue, suggests that vitamin D may play a direct or indirect role in enhancing insulin action [3].

Several studies have shown that vitamin D influences both insulin secretion and sensitivity. Mechanistically, vitamin D may affect insulin gene expression, insulin receptor expression, and intracellular calcium concentrations—all of which are critical to glucose homeostasis [4]. Additionally, vitamin D exerts anti-inflammatory effects, perhaps reducing the long-term low-grade inflammation often linked to type 2 diabetes and insulin resistance [3, 5].

Despite these proposed mechanisms, observational and interventional studies investigating this have shown conflicting findings about the relationship between insulin resistance and vitamin D levels. Serum 25(OH)D levels and insulin resistance indicators like HOMA-IR and fasting insulin have been found to significantly inversely correlate in some studies, but not in others.

For example, a randomized placebo-controlled trial conducted by Wallace et al. (2019) found no significant effect of vitamin D supplementation on insulin sensitivity in a pre-diabetic population [6].

Given the growing prevalence of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) and vitamin D deficiency in the Indian population, there is a compelling need to investigate their potential correlation. In this study, blood vitamin D levels and insulin resistance in type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) patients are assessed, and the results are compared with those of healthy controls.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A case-control study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry and Medicine at Sharda Hospital, Greater Noida, after obtaining ethical clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee. A total of 90 participants were recruited and divided into two groups: 45 patients diagnosed with T2DM based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA) 2022 criteria, and 45 normal healthy subjects of the same age and sex were treated as the control.

Inclusion criteria were included age between 30–60 years, confirmed diagnosis of T2DM, and no intake of vitamin D supplements for at least four weeks before enrolment. Exclusion criteria included the presence of chronic illnesses such as renal or liver disease, pregnancy, long-term steroid use, cancer, and other comorbid conditions associated with T2DM.

Following written informed consent fasting blood samples were collected from all participants. Blood glucose was estimated using the Glucose Oxidase-Peroxidase (GOD-POD) method. Serum insulin and vitamin D concentrations were measured using the ELISA technique. The Homeostasis Model Assessment for Insulin Resistance (HOMA-IR) was calculated using the following formula [7]:

$$\text{HOMA IR} = \frac{\text{Fasting Insulin } (\mu\text{IU/ml}) \times \text{Fasting Glucose (mmol/l)}}{22.5}$$

RESULTS

Fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels were significantly higher among diabetic patients (199.11 ± 57.7 mg/dl) compared to healthy controls (91.2 ± 11.21 mg/dl), with a p-value < 0.001 (Table 1).

This reflects poor glycaemic control among the diabetic subjects.

Vitamin D levels were significantly lower in T2DM cases (11.23 ± 5.1 ng/ml) as compared to controls (15.12 ± 6.76 ng/ml), with a p-value of 0.003 (Table 2).

Notably, 95.56% of diabetic individuals were vitamin D deficient (<20 ng/ml), whereas 86.67% of controls fell into the same category, although this difference was not statistically significant.

Serum insulin levels were found to be lower in T2DM patients (12 ± 5.09 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$) as compared to healthy controls (15.38 ± 4.34 $\mu\text{IU/ml}$), with a significant p-value of 0.003 (Table 3).

However, HOMA-IR values, a measure of insulin resistance, were notably higher in the diabetic group (5.77 ± 2.57) than in the control group (3.34 ± 1.07), indicating increased insulin resistance ($p < 0.001$) (Table 4).

Table 1: Fasting blood glucose levels in healthy controls and Type 2 diabetic Patients.

Fasting blood sugar	Controls (n=45)	Cases (n=45)	P value
Normal {74 to 100 mg/dl}	35 (77.78%)	0 (0%)	<.001
Deranged {>100 mg/dl}	10 (22.22%)	45 (100%)	
Mean \pm SD	91.2 ± 11.21	199.11 ± 57.7	<.001
Median (25th-75 th percentile)	92(82-99)	188(162-209)	
Range	74-110	126-416	

Table 2: Serum vitamin D levels in healthy controls and Type 2 diabetic Patients.

Vitamin D (ng/ml)	Controls (n=45)	Cases (n=45)	P value
Mean \pm SD	15.12 ± 6.76	11.23 ± 5.1	0.003
Range	5.37-40.37	2.67-26.98	

Table 3: Serum insulin levels in healthy controls and Type 2 diabetic Patients.

Insulin ($\mu\text{IU/ml}$)	Controls (n=45)	Cases (n=45)	P value
Mean \pm SD	15.38 ± 4.34	12 ± 5.09	0.003
Range	6.81-26.01	4.09-22.2	

Table 4: HOMA IR in healthy controls and Type 2 diabetic patients.

HOMA IR	Controls (n=45)	Cases (n=45)	P value
Mean \pm SD	3.34 ± 1.07	5.77 ± 2.57	<.001
Range	0.4-6	1.52-11.9	

Spearman correlation analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between serum vitamin D and insulin levels in cases ($r = 0.845$, $p < 0.001$) and a moderate positive correlation in controls ($r = 0.324$, $p = 0.030$). The correlation between vitamin D and HOMA-IR is found to be inverse ($r = -0.005$) in T2DM (Table 5).

Table 5: Correlation of vitamin D with Insulin, HOMA IR, and FBS in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus

Variables	Insulin (μ U/ml)	HOMA IR	FBS (mg/dl)
Vitamin D (ng/ml)			
Correlation coefficient	0.845	-0.005	0.269
P value	<0.001	0.974	0.074

DISCUSSION

The present study included 45 Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus subjects, consisting of 14 females, 31 males, and 45 healthy subjects, consisting of 15 females, 30 males.

In T2DM group mean fasting blood glucose levels were significantly higher (168.13 ± 49.04 mg/dl) than that of the control group (89.40 ± 9.88 mg/dl), and the difference was highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This observation aligns with the diagnostic thresholds for diabetes and indicates a clear dysregulation of glucose metabolism in newly diagnosed individuals. These results support previous Indian studies reporting similar elevations in glucose levels at diagnosis [8], [9].

The diabetic group exhibited significantly elevated fasting insulin levels (28.06 ± 10.87 μ U/ml) as compared to the control group (14.90 ± 5.72 μ U/ml) ($p < 0.001$). This suggests early-stage compensatory hyperinsulinemia, which occurs as the body attempts to counteract peripheral insulin resistance. Previous literature, including studies by Pittas et al. [10] and Mitri et al. [11], has similarly observed this trend in early T2DM cases.

HOMA-IR values were significantly higher in T2DM patients (mean = 5.77 ± 2.57) than in controls (3.34 ± 1.07) ($p < 0.001$), affirming the presence of marked insulin resistance in diabetic individuals. This is in alignment with Chiu et al. [12] and Maestro et al. [13], who demonstrated that insulin resistance is a primary pathophysiological feature of T2DM. The correlation of Serum vitamin D and HOMA-IR in T2DM was found to be inverse ($r = -0.065$). These results had some similarities with those of Frouhi et al. [15] and Chiu et al. [12], who reported an inverse correlation between vitamin D levels and insulin resistance. In addition to T2DM, this inverse relation might be related to population-specific factors, stage of disease, or other unmeasured variables such as BMI, physical activity, or calcium intake.

Serum 25(OH)D levels were significantly lower in the diabetic group (11.54 ± 5.46 ng/ml) compared to the control group (15.12 ± 6.76 ng/ml) with a p-value of 0.003, reinforcing the link between hypovitaminosis D and T2DM in Indian populations. This supports prior research by Pal et al. [14] and Holick [1], who identified vitamin D deficiency as highly prevalent in both diabetic and general populations in India.

The association analysis between vitamin D and fasting insulin produced an intriguing finding. A significant positive correlation ($r = 0.845$) was seen in the diabetic group, suggesting that lower insulin levels were linked to decreased vitamin D levels. This contradicts the findings by Chiu et al. [12] and Pittas et al. [10]. However, in newly diagnosed individuals, this relationship might reflect complex compensatory mechanisms where vitamin D modulates early β -cell function but has yet to influence peripheral insulin sensitivity significantly.

The distribution of vitamin D deficiency by gender shows that among the diabetic group, deficiency was higher in females (52.63%) than males (47.37%). This gender-based disparity could reflect socio-cultural factors affecting sun exposure and dietary intake, particularly among Indian women. Previous studies have explained various mechanisms by which vitamin D may impact insulin sensitivity. Maestro et al. [13] reported enhanced insulin receptor expression due to vitamin D, while Lemieux et

al. [16] described its role in reducing inflammatory cytokines like IL-6 and TNF- α . These cytokines are known to impair insulin signalling, especially in obese or diabetic subjects.

Nevertheless, randomized controlled trials have produced mixed results. Wallace et al. [17] found no significant improvement in insulin sensitivity after vitamin D supplementation in diabetic individuals. These inconsistencies underscore the complex, multifactorial relationship between vitamin D and insulin resistance, which may be influenced by factors like ethnicity, baseline vitamin D status, and disease stage.

The proposed biological pathways show the role of vitamin D in regulation of intracellular calcium levels which is critical for insulin exocytosis, suppression of inflammatory cytokines, and activation of vitamin D receptors (VDRs) in pancreatic β -cells. These mechanisms suggest a supportive role in maintaining insulin secretion and modulating resistance [11], [1], [16].

From a clinical standpoint, the high prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in newly diagnosed T2DM patients highlights the need for early screening and correction of vitamin D levels. Though conclusive evidence on supplementation improving insulin sensitivity remains limited, ensuring optimal vitamin D status could enhance overall metabolic and skeletal health.

CONCLUSION

This study found a considerable prevalence of vitamin D deficiency in individuals with newly diagnosed type 2 diabetes, especially in females. This is probably because of the disparities in sun exposure associated with lifestyle. Vitamin D and fasting insulin levels were positively correlated, which might suggest that vitamin D plays a part in early β -cell activity, there was significant inverse correlation relationship between vitamin D and HOMA-IR, which suggests that vitamin D has effect on peripheral insulin resistance. According to these results, vitamin D may help insulin secretion more than sensitivity. Notwithstanding drawbacks like the limited sample size and the absence of confounder data, the findings demonstrate the need for early vitamin D screening to treat diabetes.

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